

SUSTAINABLE LIGHTWEIGHT BIOCOMPOSITES FROM TOUGHENED POLYPROPYLENE AND BIOCARBON FOR AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The current state of polymer composites in the automotive industry is based on a linear economy concept which raises serious sustainability issues for many automakers around the world. Several parts in a vehicle are now made of polymer composites which constitute a sizable portion of the car's weight. These parts, being interior decorative elements or impact absorber bumpers, are normally made from a petroleum-based matrix filled with non-renewable fillers such as talc and glass fiber. The advent of new regulations in the automotive industry such as Corporate Average Fuel Economy (CAFÉ) standard pushes for more lightweight and eco-friendly materials. One solution to this problem is to replace the traditional fillers with biobased fillers which can satisfy the automotive requirements. The challenge would be to fulfill the required mechanical properties especially the stiffness-toughness balance in such biocomposites. Biocarbon being a biobased material and a product of biomass pyrolysis as well as falling in line with the circular economy concept fits well into this solution. Recent research on biocarbon composites showed that unlike carbon black it could successfully reinforce plastics even at high loading levels. However, creating a biocarbon based composite with balanced stiffness and toughness has remained a challenge so far. The present work investigates a novel polypropylene-biocarbon based biocomposite with high impact toughness. By tuning the properties of the biocarbon, use of an α -olefin elastomer and proper compatibilizer the notched Izod impact properties of the composites significantly improved (600 J/m) without any significant loss in the stiffness and strength of the composites. The morphological analysis of the fractured surfaces revealed the underlying mechanisms for such an improvement. The changes in the interface of the biocarbon were responsible for super-toughening effect in such composites. These results demonstrate the potential of biocarbon as a replacement of traditional filler in toughened PP composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

World's linear petroleum-based economy has led to the excessive usage of non-renewable resources, production of non-biodegradable wastes, and emission of greenhouse gasses (GHG) which raises serious sustainability issues for the current and future generations [1]. The oil and gas are mainly used for transportation, electricity and heat generation, and production of chemicals including plastics. Several approaches have been initiated to address each of the mentioned sectors. Formation of biorefineries, enforcement of new fuel economy standards and utilization of bioplastics and biocomposites are a few examples of these approaches. The biorefineries will address the renewable fuel production for transportation and energy sectors. At the same time, fuel economy standards such as corporate average fuel economy (CAFE) limits the fuel consumption of vehicles. Bioplastics and biocomposites, on the other hand, tend to replace traditional petroleum-based materials.

Statistical data showed that the transportation sector is responsible for about 60% of the total world oil demand and it would most likely continue to grow steadily in the future [2]. The significant share of the transportation sector in oil consumption has led to an increasing interest in obtaining biofuel from renewable materials and more specifically non-food resources lignocellulosic biomass [3]. With this concept, the current linear economy can be replaced by a circular bioeconomy in which the energy and fuel will be harvested from nature and will be returned to the environment without producing an excess amount of GHG or wastes. Among all the available techniques, thermochemical pathway showed promising results for obtaining biofuel and bioenergy from biomass [4].

Pyrolysis is a thermochemical conversion process in which the raw biomass is heated in the absence of oxygen and produces bio-oil, synthetic gas (syngas) and solid char known as biocarbon. The syngas can be utilized as bioenergy for heating or electricity production. The bio-oil is a liquid fuel which can be used directly or refined further for higher end applications. The oil can also break down to chemicals to produce material building blocks such as monomers for plastic synthesis. However, the biocarbon which is a carbon-rich solid with relatively low heating value did not find a value-added application to contribute to the whole process. Depending on the type and conditions of pyrolysis, the biocarbon production can vary between 12 to 35% of the yield. The significant amount of char production challenges the long-term sustainability of pyrolysis units, and it is against the circular economy concept.

Utilization of biocarbon in automotive plastic parts could be a possible solution for finding a high demand and value-added application for this material. Initial characterization of biocarbon showed promising intrinsic properties which can be useful for this specific application. The atomic force microscopy and nanoindentation measurements of the biocarbon's modulus showed that the stiffness could vary between 5 to 25 GPa depending on the biomass source and the pyrolysis conditions [5,6]. Brewer et al. [7] measured the density of the biocarbon with deferent methods; these results revealed that the non-graphitic biocarbon has a density of 1.4 g/cm³ which is almost half of the conventional mineral filler used in plastic industry. Furthermore, the inherent properties of the biocarbon such as chemical functionality, surface area, porosity, stiffness, heat and thermal conductivity can be controlled through the pyrolysis process [8,9]. This control can provide a low cost and eco-friendly method to tune the properties for the specific target in polymer composites.

Use of biocarbon in biocomposites could results in lighter weight parts with less petroleum based resin while satisfying the application gap for the pyrolysis byproduct. The lighter weight of the parts contributes to the better fuel economy for cars. Overall, this approach will be in line with the circular economy concept by contributing to the sustainability of biorefineries, reducing the fuel consumption in vehicles and lowering the petroleum-based content of the composites.

The main challenge in producing new biocomposites for automotive application is to reach the same level of performance as the conventional composites with mineral fillers such as talc or glass fiber. The most important aspect would be satisfying the mechanical properties requirements especially the stiffness-toughness balance [10].

In this study, miscanthus based biocarbon were utilized in toughened PP composites targeting automotive parts application. The stiffness-toughness has been assessed through the notched Izod impact strength and tensile modulus of the composites. The underlying changes in morphologies have been discussed and related to the mechanical properties. Finally, the performance of the biocarbon based biocomposites was compared to the industry reference material.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

In this study, miscanthus biocarbon (BC) which was hammer milled to $\sim 400 \mu\text{m}$ (1/64 in.), received from Competitive Green Technologies, Leamington, ON, Canada. This biocarbon was produced through a slow pyrolysis process at $\sim 630^\circ\text{C}$. In this process after a pre-drying cycle, 300 kg of the chopped miscanthus grass conveyed through the pyrolysis chamber using an auger system which took 15 min from the entrance to exit. The whole chamber was set to be at the temperatures mentioned above.

The as received biocarbon batch was sieved to particle size ranges of 106-125, <75 and smaller than $20 \mu\text{m}$ separately using a Ro-tap sieve shaker (W.S. Tyler, OH, USA) fitted with appropriate Tyler sieves. The ball milled samples were prepared using a planetary milling machine (Retsch PM100, Germany). The milling media was 200g of 10 mm zirconium oxide balls. The as received biocarbon was milled for 24h at sun wheel speed of 300 rpm.

Injection molding grade of polypropylene (PP) pellets, (trade name 1335Z) was a product of Pinnacle Polymers LLC., LA, USA. The melt flow index (MFI) at $230^\circ\text{C}/2.16 \text{ Kg}$ and density of PP were $35 \text{ g}/10 \text{ min}$ and $0.9 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$ according to the materials datasheet, respectively. The polyolefin elastomer used was an ethylene-octene copolymer (POE) a product of Dow Chemical Company (trade name Engage 8137) in the form of pellets. The MFI at $190^\circ\text{C}/2.16 \text{ kg}$ and density of POE were $13 \text{ g}/10\text{min}$ and $0.866 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$ respectively. A maleic anhydride grafted PP (MAPP) copolymer was added to produce preferential adhesion between the particles and PP. The MAPP used in this study was Fusabond P353 a product of DuPont (Wilmington, DE). The industry reference material was a 30% mineral thermoplastic polyolefin elastomer (TPE) classified as Ford Motor company material under WSS-M4D954-A.

All the formulations were melt processed at 190°C , at a screw speed of 100 rpm (co-rotating) for 120 s in DSM Xplore micro compounder with length over diameter ratio (L/D) of 18 (DSM Xplore, the Netherlands). The molten compound was then transferred to the DSM Xplore 12 cc injection molding machine to make test specimens. The injection, packing and holding pressures and duration were 4, 8, 8 bar and 4, 6 and 10 s respectively. Mold temperature was kept constant at 40°C during all injections. All the biocomposites were prepared by mixing 20 wt.% of the biocarbon with a 70/30 PP/POE blend. In the case of compatibilized samples, 5 wt.% of the PP was replaced by the MAPP.

The fracture surface morphologies of samples were gold coated and observed under scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Phenom ProX (Phenom World BV, Netherlands) equipped with a backscattering electron (BSE).

Tensile properties of the composites were measured by Instron universal testing machine (Norwood, MA). Type IV specimens were tested as per the ASTM D638-14 protocol with a test speed of $50 \text{ mm}/\text{min}$ at room temperature and with 50% relative humidity. Flexural properties were measured as per ASTM D790-15 (procedure B); with a crosshead speed of $14 \text{ mm}/\text{min}$ and a span length of 52 mm. The impact strength of the samples was measured in accordance with ASTM D256-10. The samples were notched 48 hours before testing. The tests were conducted on a TMI monitor impact tester (Testing Machine Inc. DE, USA) with five ft.lb pendulum at room temperature. Five replicates were tested for each of the mechanical tests.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To investigate the effect of biocarbon as a new filler in the toughened PP matrix, a few aspects needed to be considered first. Filler aspects such as particle size, filler surface chemistry and compatibility with the matrix need to be evaluated first. Figure 1 shows the effect of particle size on the stiffness and toughness of the toughened PP composites. The results suggest that the reduction in the particle size did not significantly affect the stiffness of the composites and the marginal improvement in the modulus in small particles are not of any practical importance. The independence of the modulus from particle size in composites with micron-sized fillers has been established before [11]. On the other hand, the impact toughness changed substantially when the biocarbon particles were added to the matrix. The impact toughness dropped initially with the addition of biocarbon and reduced further as the particle size reduced to 20 μm . However, the ball-milled particles changed this trend and caused a significant improvement in the impact toughness. This behavior can be related to the presence of defects in biocarbon structure [5]. The holes and pores in the structure of a biocarbon can be seen in Figure 3. The ball milling process can break the particles from their defective sites and hence produce particles with less flaw at the end. Moreover, the particle will tend to be more round after the milling which reduces the stress concentration caused by sharp edges. Ogunsuna et al. observed a similar trend when biocarbon was added to the polyamide matrix [12]. The loss of aspect ratio as a result of milling process can be the reason behind the slight decrease in the modulus of the ball milled samples.

Figure 1: The effect of particle size the stiffness and toughness of the high-temperature biocarbon based biocomposites (with compatibilizer); (A) PP/POE, (B) 106-125 μm , (C) <75 μm , (D) <20 μm , (E) ball-milled particles.

The second important factor is the compatibility of the biocarbon with the matrix. The effect of this feature can be observed through biocarbons with different surface functionality and their interaction with the compatibilizer and the matrix. Figure 2 shows the stiffness-toughness balance in biocomposites with different biocarbon. In this series, the biocarbons were pyrolyzed at different temperatures. Therefore, the biocarbons are fundamentally different regarding their available functional groups and their corresponding amount. Detailed analysis of the biocarbon composition and their functionality has been published elsewhere [13]. Previous work of the authors revealed that the

LTBc surface has certain functional groups such as carboxyl while the HTBc mainly consists of aromatic carbon [13]. Similar to particle size effect the difference in the chemical functionality of the biocarbon did not affect the stiffness of the composites to a large extent. However, the impact toughness of the composites was more sensitive to the compatibility. The addition of compatibilizer significantly improves the impact toughness of the HTBc composites, this can be observed by comparing the results of the uncompatibilized and compatibilized HTBc composites (B and C) in Figure 2. The presence of the functional group in LTBc makes the biocarbon incompatible with the matrix. Although the addition of compatibilizer improves the impact toughness, it could not recover the properties to the original values of the matrix. The significant difference in impact properties is due to the specific morphology of phases in biocomposites and the strength of the interaction between the component of the matrix (PP and POE) with the biocarbon [13, 14]. The improvement in the interface of the biocarbon was responsible for super-toughening effect in such composites (Figure 3).

Figure 2: The effect of biocarbon surface functionality and compatibilization on the biocomposites properties; (A) PP/POE, (B) HTBc, (C) HTBc with compatibilizer, (D) LTBc

Figure 3: SEM images of PP/POE/biocarbon biocomposites with (a) poor (with MAPP) and (b) enhanced interface (without MAPP).

Apart from the stiffness-toughness balance, other performance attributes were also measured and compared to a 30% mineral filled industrial reference material for injection moldable parts. Density was one the important targets of biocarbon biocomposite development. The processability is another important factor determining the processing technique of the materials. Usually, this property is measured through the melt flow index testing. In Figure 4 the performance attributes of biocarbon based biocomposites compared to an industry reference material used for automotive parts.

Figure 4: Performance comparison between 30% talc filled industry reference compound and the biocarbon based biocomposites.

The results suggest that by proper choice of the biocarbon and suitable compatibilization, biocarbon based biocomposites can perform better or at the same level as the current mineral filled composites in the automotive industry.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The use of biocarbon as a filler in composite formulations for automotive parts has investigated with regards to the particles size and compatibility of the particles with the matrix. It was found that reduction of the structural defects by means of ball milling can significantly improve the performance of these composites. Moreover, the compatibility plays a critical role in the impact toughness of the biocomposites. The combination of a compatibilizer and high temperature processed biocarbon has resulted in the best impact toughness.

These results demonstrate the potential performance of biocarbon as a replacement of traditional filler in toughened PP composites. This could create a high demand application for the biocarbon leading to a more sustainable biorefinery approach for producing biofuel. Furthermore, the lower density of the biocomposites as compare to conventional composites used in automotive industry can contribute to the better fuel economy of cars.

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